

Growth Kinetic Model for Microalgae Cultivation in Open Raceway Ponds: A System Dynamics Tool

Francesco ROMAGNOLI^{1*}, Anton Rayan Priyasad Perera WEERASURIYA-ARACHCHIGE²,
Riccardo PAOLI³, Maksims FEOFILOVS⁴, Baiba IEVINA⁵

^{1,4,5} *Institute of Energy Systems and Environment, Riga Technical University, Āzenes iela 12/1,
Riga, LV-1048, Latvia*

² *Water Systems and Biotechnology Institute, Riga Technical University, Āzenes iela 6a/6b,
Riga, LV-1048, Latvia*

³ *Università Degli Studi Dell'insubria, Via Ravasi 2, Varese, 2110, Italy*

Abstract – Microalgae culture has the potential to play an essential role in the application of circular economy principles. Microalgae cultivation allows utilizing industrial side-waste streams while ensuring biomass for a wide range of applications in the industrial sector. Specifically, cultivation in outdoor open raceway ponds are a preferred solution due to low costs, ease of operation and large-scale application. However, the economic viability of the cultivation system largely depends on the amount of biomass produced, the technology implemented and the microalgae species and strains. For this purpose, screening of numerous physical, chemical, and environmental factors affecting microalgae growth must be performed before implementing large-scale microalgae cultivation systems. Furthermore, to obtain the highest biomass yield, the design and operating parameters for open raceway pond cultivation must be investigated in depth. Therefore, this study proposes a kinetic growth model for microalgae cultivation in open raceway ponds based on System Dynamics modelling approach. The proposed model aims at overcoming the major problems of existing growth evaluation tools such as separate assessment of different parameters, high complexity, time consumption and other challenges. The proposed system dynamics model proves to be a simple yet powerful tool for modelling the behaviour of algae biomass in an open raceway pond.

Keywords – Biogas; causal loop diagram; computational fluid dynamics; microalgae; modelling; system dynamics

1. INTRODUCTION

Microalgae are a bioresource with a versatile role in the natural environment that maintains the balance of biochemical flows of nutrients (i.e., N, P) [1]. However, anthropogenic activities undermine the natural balance of biochemical flows, leading people to consider promising the use of microalgae-based wastewater remediation technologies or side-stream flows (e.g., digestate from biogas plant) [2].

The use of microalgae application for side-stream waste and waste treatment was discovered more than 50 years ago [1] became a widely used sustainable application in the last decade [3]. The goal is to reach an engineered microalgae growing system acting as bio-filter for both nutrient recirculation and CO₂ fixation in the microalgae biomass [4]. In fact,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: francesco.romagnoli@rtu.lv

autotrophic microalgae use carbon dioxide as the primary substrate in the photosynthesis process to fix it in biomass. Once a waste carbon source is coupled with the microalgae cultivation process, the waste carbon can be converted into valuable microalgae biomass, becoming a promising source of value-added bioactive for food and nutrition [5], [6]. Nevertheless, the economic payback on microalgae cultivation systems still largely depends on the amount of the algal biomass produced and on the efficiency of the growing systems [5]. In this direction, using models to predict algae biomass productivity and initially screen potentially usable microalgae plays an essential economic role when designing and operating such a system. Since microbiology growth kinetics is a complex biochemical process, these models rely on cellular growth kinetic models developed over decades with the help of laboratory experiments.

However, when scaling the laboratory systems to large scale algae productions, these models have certain limitations primarily associated with validating experimental results in the pilot pre-industrial scale. The researchers use different mathematical tools for growth kinetic modelling implementing complex differential equation solvers [5]. Although these tools are reliable, they are rather complex to use, and the implementation of a specific kinetic model for specific microalgae growing conditions is time-consuming. This aspect is paramount when scaling up from laboratory to large-scale cultivation. Hence there is a growing need for developing a user-friendly growth kinetic model. This study aims to develop a kinetic growth model for microalgae cultivation in open raceway ponds using a System Dynamics approach and overcome current models' limitations.

2. MICROALGAE GROWTH MODELLING

2.1. *Microalgae Growth Characteristics*

Microalgae are considered fast-growing unicellular species. If the conditions are optimal, these cells continuously increase their population by duplicating. Microalgae biomass is mainly produced by photosynthesis, which utilizes inorganic substances (including CO₂). When compared to other photosynthetic organisms such as terrestrial plants, microalgae highlight the following growth characteristics [4]: higher growth rate and shorter reproduction time, higher photosynthetic efficiency, less space required, and no need for soil substrate to grow on.

Similarly, with most other microorganisms, microalgae typically follow a general growth dynamic behaviour, which has five phases in the case of microalgae [7]. The first is the lag phase which occurs when an algae culture is moved from a plate to the liquid growth media. The growth of culture is slow due to the lack of physiological response of cell metabolism to growth, such as producing enzymes required for cellular division. After the microalgae are acclimatized to their environment it follows an exponential growth. The growth rate relies on the accessibility of nutrients, light and many other factors. The growth declines when the limit or unbalance of physical and chemical factors such as light, pH, Carbon is reached. During the stationary phase the growth rate is equal to zero. This occurs when the algal cells are not growing anymore or the number of cells growing equals the number of cells dying at a unit time. The last phase is the decline, during which algae cells die due to various factors such as nutrient depletion, cellular ageing, toxicity, the effect of temperature and pH. In a batch culture death phase usually occurs when all the nutrients are consumed. At this phase, cell density rapidly decreases as culture collapses.

The effectiveness of microalgae cultivation relies on the characteristics of several environmental, physical, and biological factors and the design of the pond. The main

parameters used are concentration of algae, light, temperature, pH, salinity, concentrations of nutrients, and toxic elements [8]. The following sections will present the main key empirical equations further implemented in the developed System Dynamics model.

2.1.1. Concentration of Microalgae

When designing a cultivation system for microalgae, the aim is to create conditions that allow maintaining the exponential phase for a longer period. Hence describing the mathematical relationship of the biomass concentration (C_b) over time is very important. The kinetic equations proposed in the developed model in this study are based on the exponential growth of biomass in time [9]. The change of biomass at a given time is a function of the biomass specific growth rate (μ), which can be expressed as:

$$\mu = \frac{1}{C} \cdot \frac{dC}{dt}, \quad (1)$$

where

- C Microalgae concentration at a given time t , expressed as $g\ l^{-1}$;
- μ Specific growth rate, d^{-1} or hr^{-1} .

The biomass productivity (P_b) ($g\ l^{-1}$ per day or $g\ l^{-1}$ per hour), which is the amount of biomass generated after a specific time interval, it can be expressed as:

$$P_b = \mu \cdot C_b = \frac{dC}{dt}, \quad (2)$$

where C_b is initial biomass concentration, $g\ l^{-1}$.

The optimal growth rate is reached when the microorganism grows unrestrained by nutrient limits or the accumulation of waste products. The growth rate of the number of cells, or dry weight, per unit of time during the exponential growth is proportional to the number of cells present in the culture at the start of any time unit (C_0). Hence, by integrating the Eq. (2) from $t = 0$ to $t = t$, the microalgae concentration (C_t) after a Δt is expressed as:

$$C_t = C_0 \cdot e^{\mu \cdot \Delta t}, \quad (3)$$

and the growth rate (μ) is expressed as:

$$\mu = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{C_t}{C_0}\right)}{\Delta t} = \frac{\ln(C_t) - \ln(C_0)}{\Delta t}, \quad (4)$$

where

- C_0 Initial biomass concentration, $g\ l^{-1}$;
- C_t Biomass concentration at time t , $g\ l^{-1}$;
- Δt Time duration.

However, some cells die in a microalgae culture due to cellular ageing, even if the conditions are ideal. Hence the cumulative biomass productivity is described as follows:

$$P_b = (\mu - m) \cdot C_b, \quad (5)$$

where

m	Mortality rate, d^{-1} or hr^{-1} ;
P_b	Biomass productivity, $g\ l^{-1}d^{-1}$ or $g\ l^{-1}hr^{-1}$;
C_b	Biomass concentration, $g\ l^{-1}$.

The mortality rate is typically constant when the growth conditions are not inhibited. The availability of nutrients and light, together with reactor's parameters, play a key role in microalgae kinetics (i.e. residence time, air to liquid mass transfer rate, medium homogeneity).

2.1.2. Nutrients

Most of the sustainable algae cultivation applications in open raceway pond systems utilise wastewater as a nutrient source. The wastewater generally contains high concentrations of nutrients; hence nutrient starvation is not a problem when wastewater is used in microalgae cultivation systems.

For algae growth, nitrogen is a key nutrient. In microalgae the nitrogen amount of algal dry matter is about 7 % (w/w). The increase in nitrogen level until a certain threshold leads to a more outstanding production of cells and proteins and greater chlorophyll synthesis. The lack of nitrogen leads to a significant reduction in lipids polyunsaturated fatty acids) with a direct effect on the photosynthetic and cellular activities [10]. Another important nutrient for microalgae growth is phosphorus and accounts for 1 % (w/w) of the dry algae biomass. Phosphorus is involved in several metabolic pathways and cellular regulations of microalgae. Unfortunately, in most algal cultivation systems, phosphorus is the limiting nutrient. Phosphorus also plays a vital role in lipid accumulation in microalgae cells, which is the most value-added product in microalgae applications [10]–[12].

2.1.3. Light

In photosynthetic cultures such as microalgae and phytoplankton, the cells use light energy for cellular maintenance and new biomass production [13]. Therefore, biomass productivity and cell growth rates are directly related to the light energy available. Light energy can be natural (solar) or from artificial systems in fluorescent tubing around or inside the reactor. Novel systems embed light sources inside the culture media in the form of LED or fibre optics. The design of lighting for a microalgae cultivation system must consider several different factors, such as optical path, optical depth (which characterizes the degree of transparency of the medium), and the illuminated surface ratio by volume culture [10], [14].

2.2. Growth Kinetic Models

Kinetic model aims to describe how the microalgae population behaves in a particular environment over a given time. Such models express the relationship of parameters, which affect the growth rate of microalgae. There is a large variety of kinetic models for understanding the growth of microalgae in natural habitats. Mainly they can be divided into two types of models: descriptive and explanatory. Explanatory models are mainly developed to explain the cause or fundamental systematic behaviour. Most of these models have complex structures and maths, but to a certain extent can be simplified. On the other hand, descriptive models are developed to predict system performance and not to explain mechanisms. This category covers the most empirically developed kinetic models [15].

2.2.1. Single Substrate Models

The growth of microalgae in aquatic environments depends on nutrients' availability, such as Nitrogen, Phosphorus, and Carbon under light-saturating conditions. Often kinetic growth models are expressed according to a single concentration of nutrients. The most popular formula is Monod equation [16]–[18], which is expressed below:

$$\mu = \mu_{\max} \cdot \frac{S}{k_s + S}, \quad (6)$$

where

- μ Specific growth rate, d^{-1} or hr^{-1} ;
- μ_{\max} Maximum specific growth rate, d^{-1} or hr^{-1} ;
- S Concentration of the substrate, g/l ;
- k_s Half-saturation constant, g/l .

The maximum specific growth rate is the maximum growth rate a certain microalgae strain resembles under ideal nutrient and light conditions. Half saturation constant (k_s) in microbiology refers to the substrate concentration required to reach the growth rate at half of the maximum specific growth rate. The Monod model is suitable to describe growth in low and modest nutrient concentrations but is limited in describing the inhibition of microalgae growth due to high nutrient levels.

2.2.2. Kinetic Model Attenuation Models

A specific level of light, called saturated level of light, is required for microalgae to reach the maximum growth rate. If the intensity of light exceeds the level of saturation well, light inhibits growth. On the other hand, if the light intensity is below the level of saturation, light limits the growth [19].

When cultivating microalgae in conventional open raceway ponds, the light is received only from the top surface of the pond. When the light photons penetrate the pond, the intensity decreases due to absorption by the algae cells which the light passes. This is called light attenuation. Also, the incident light could reflect away from the thick top layer [20].

Light-based kinetic models' growth rates are related to the incident light intensity with two parameters: intensity and saturation constant. When the light intensity incident is less than saturation constant, the growth according to first-order kinetics is limited by light. When light intensity incidents become higher than saturations constant, growth is independent of light saturation and a specific growth rate. This is case of the Steele equation [15], [21], which fits the photo-inhibition effect and can be expressed with the Eq. (7), considering I_{opt} as the optimum light intensity for the specific microalgae strain.

$$\mu = \mu_{\max} \frac{I}{I_{opt}} e^{\left(1 - \frac{I}{I_{opt}}\right)} \quad (7)$$

In Steele equation, once the light intensity reaches I_{opt} , the growth rate will be at its maximum value, and any change in light intensity will result in a lower growth rate [15].

The parameter “I” mentioned in this model is a luminous intensity defined as the light irradiance received by an algae cell. This term is doubtful as there is no practical way to measure the amount of light irradiance received by each algae cell.

The Beer-Lambert law [22] expresses the formula to calculate light intensity at a given depth of a microalgae raceway pond accounting for the gradual decay of light [23], described as:

$$I_z = I_0 e^{-k_a \cdot B \cdot z}, \tag{8}$$

where

- I_z Local light intensity received by algal cells at z depth, $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$;
- Z Depth, m;
- I_0 Light intensity at the external surface of the pond, $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$;
- k_a Biomass light absorption (extinction) coefficient, $\text{m}^2 \text{kg}^{-1}$;
- B Algal concentration, kg m^{-3} .

Unit ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) is typically used for Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR). It is a measure of the energy absorbed in plants from solar radiation by chlorophyll A and B. It is, in fact, a measure of the energy effectively available for photosynthesis. The biomass light absorption (extinction) coefficient (k_a) is a measure of how strongly a chemical species or material absorbs light at a specific wavelength. It is the inherent property of the particular chemical species, which depends on their chemical composition and structure [23].

2.2.3. Growth Kinetic Model Considering Multiple Factors

In the natural environment, the limitation is more common than in commercial cultivation systems to limit both nutrients and light on the growth of microalgae, which is also called co-limitation. Co-limitation models can be arranged according to two distinctive models, thresholds, and multiplicative models [15].

The threshold model, also known as the minimum law, relies on the assumption that the most limited resource affects the total rate of growth. The final mathematical expression is therefore identical to the growth models that take one factor into account. The threshold model can be expressed as:

$$\mu = \mu_{\max, \min} [f(x_1), f(x_2), f(x_3), \dots, f(x_i)], \tag{9}$$

where $\mu_{\max, \min}$ is the maximum growth rate for the most limited resource and $f(x_i)$ is the function of multiple limited resources and light intensity.

For example, when considering outdoor open raceway cultivation utilising side-waste stream rich of nutrients, the light becomes the limiting factor that affects the growth rate. Hence when modelling the growth rate, light limit μ_{\max} for the maximum growth rate should be considered. The cultivation systems, mostly photobioreactors, which utilise secondary treated wastewater, are often limited in phosphorus. Therefore, when modelling those systems, the maximum growth rate should be changed.

On the other hand, the multiplicative model assumes that all resources contribute equally to the growth of microalgae. In the study of [24] a multiplicative model is presented for microalgae growth, considering multiple environmental factors such as light intensity, temperature, nutrients and pH. In such model all resources will simultaneously influence the overall growth rate as described in Eq. (10):

$$\mu = \mu_{\max} [f(x_1), f(x_2), f(x_3), \dots, f(x_i)], \tag{10}$$

where μ_{\max} is the cumulative maximum specific growth rate.

Such models frequently describe nitrogen, carbon dioxide and light co-limitation. The Monod formula is the most common expression of individual growth factors in multiplicative models [15].

Hence, the growth rate of microalgae is disturbed by several limiting resources and environmental factors. Though there are several models developed, most of them are limited to laboratory-scale systems. The most significant setback of existing models is that their use for subsequent applications is limited.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Goal and System Boundaries

The goal of this research aims to create a transparent and straightforward yet reliable microalgae growth kinetics model with consideration of different parameters. Specifically, the model is developed for microalgae cultivation in an outdoor open raceway pond. For modelling purposes, the hypothetical system boundaries are assumed to include Microalgae cultivation in the pond, solar irradiation, nutrient and CO₂ supply (see Fig. 1). The mass and energy transfer are considered only between the identified sub-systems within system boundaries.

Fig. 1. Open raceway pond as a biological system.

Microalgae cultivation in any outdoor open raceway pond can distinguish 3 phases: fill, react and discharge (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Operational phases of a discontinuous batch algae reactor.

Initially, a small amount of algae population is present in the reactor, and the pond is filled with nutrients. This is assumed to be the fill phase. Then the suspension is continuously mixed

by the paddlewheel. During that time, microalgae present in the reactor consume the nutrients and the carbon present in their aquatic environment and increase their population. This process is happening in the *react* phase. At the end of the reaction, the algae suspension is removed from the pond. This is the *discharge* phase.

Some of the algae could recycle back to the reactor for the next cycle. However, this study's growth model is focused on the microalgae population's dynamic behaviour during the react phase. Thus, fill and discharge phases and recycling of microalgae after discharge is not considered in this study.

3.2. Assumptions and Limitation

According to the definition of system boundaries following assumptions are made when building and running the model:

1. The microalgae culture in the outdoor open raceway pond is a monoculture strain. There is no interaction between other microorganisms such as bacteria;
2. There is no effect from evaporation during the running phase. The mass inside the system is treated as conserved (closed system);
3. The only causes affecting the growth rate of microalgae is temperature, substrate available in the reactor and the light received by the microalgae;
4. The light available on the surface of the pond (I_0) is constant during the time period. Day-night or dark-light cycles are not considered;
5. The open raceway pond is treated as an ideal continuously stirred tank reactor where microalgae concentration through the pond is homogeneous;
6. Light reflection is neglected.

Fig. 3. Dividing the raceway pond into layers along with its depth.

The model is built according to the assumption that the microalgae cells' light (I) depends on the culture depth (z). For this purpose, algae concentration in each predefined equally distributed layer of the pond (dz) is considered in the model structure as shown in Fig. 3. This allows considering a continuous growth rate change at different depths of the pond.

By modelling the growth rate at each layer of the pond (dz) it is possible to screen out the optimum height of the open raceway pond or, the maximum biomass that must be maintained in the pond to have a considerable light penetration for efficient growth of microalgae. Ideally, the dz values should be infinitely small for smoother integration of model calculation for algae growth in the whole pond. However, within the limits of the study the pond is divided into eight depth layers.

3.3. System Dynamics Modelling

System Dynamics modelling is selected to create the microalgae growth kinetic model. System Dynamics is a scientific approach, originally developed by Jay W. Forrester in the mid-1950s. This approach is an integrated part of system thinking which studies whole system by its components, and interactions within these components. System Dynamics is generally used to address the problems arising from complex systems, characterized by an underlying causal structure of accumulation processes that causes lags, feedback, non-linearity and uncertainty [25]. System Dynamics has been demonstrated to be a consistent approach to simulate the behaviour of microbiological systems such as activated sludge wastewater treatment plants [26]. For this reason, has been selected to create the model proposed in

Within the application of System Dynamics a Causal loop diagram (CLD) for the microalgae growth kinetic mode has been developed (see Fig. 4).

The microalgae growth kinetic model based on the CLD is built with components defined in System Dynamics approach as stocks and flows. A stock is a part of the system that accumulates the effects of other variables over time and flows represent the rate at which the stock is changing at any given time [25]. Even though an outdoor open raceway pond is a complex biological system, using System Dynamics, it can be characterized and modelled by implementing a relatively small number of stocks & flow that generate the chain of the causal relationships. The results analysis using System Dynamics modelling allows one to analyse the dynamic behaviour of algae concentration depending on different factors. The software used for the creation of the model was *Stella Architect* ©.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Casual Loop Diagram (CLD)

As mentioned in section 2, the effectiveness of microalgae cultivation mainly depends on a specific parameter, namely: concentration of algae, light, temperature, pH, salinity, concentrations of nutrients, and toxic elements.

According to the co-limitation approach of the factors influencing microalgae growth in the pond, the identification of the main feedback loops for the model was based on the kinetics model as described in section 2 are represented in the CLD presented in Fig. 4.

The implemented kinetics to develop the CLD for the SD algae growth model are shown in Fig. 4. The CLD includes five feedback loops which mostly relay about the effects on the growth rate of the microalgae. The kinetic equations proposed in the model follow an exponential biomass growth in time relationship. During the exponential growth phase, the algal cells grow and divide exponentially before the linear growing phase occurs when growth slows down due to light limitation effect, or nutrients or inhibitors become a constraint. During this phase the specific growth rate (μ) can be defined according to Eq. (1). From this equation would be possible to calculate the overall microalgae population by the biomass productivity defined in Eq. (2). This effect is represented with the reinforcing loop R1: the higher the growth rate, the higher the microalgae population's increase.

According to the Steele growth model, as defined in Eq. (7), the light intensity (I) will increase the biomass concentration during a time interval Δt . Therefore, for this equation, when the growth rate reaches its maximum value, any change in light intensity will result in a lower growth rate.

It should be considered that light intensity changes over time due to the depth of the pond. This explains (balancing loop B1) in terms of the more the biomass will grow, the more the

layers in the bottom part of the ponds will have less light harvestable This behaviour is explained by the kinetics proposed Beer-Lambert law in Eq. (8).

The balancing loop B2 relies on the well-known feedback about the death and birth of living organisms: within the proposed model, the more microalgae are in the growing cultivation pond, and the more is the number of microorganisms dying due to ageing.

The CLD considers the effects of other relevant feedbacks loops. The first is the effect of the nutrient supply to the ponds in terms of N, P and C (i.e., nutrient yield in the CLD of Fig. 7). The kinetics that describe this behaviour are those proposed in Eq. (6) following the formula of Monod. For Monod equation, the maximum specific growth rate is the maximum growth rate a certain microalgae strain resembles under ideal nutrient and light conditions. As reported in section 2, the key parameters are the half-saturation constant (k_s), the concentration of the substrate and the maximum specific growth rate (μ_{max}). The balancing loop B3 affects the growth rate, and thus the microalgae population explains that the more nutrient is injected into the growing media, the more substrate concentration in the algae pond will increase, further affecting the available amount of nutrient for the microalgae population.

Fig. 4. CLD for algae population behaviour in an open raceway pond.

The last presented feedback loop in the proposed CLD is related to the amount of dissolved Carbon concentration in the growing pond relied upon the pH level in the growing media. One of the underlying parameters which affect the growth is the pH. This parameter has a direct effect on microalgae cell metabolism and biomass formation. Even though each microalgae strain has a narrow range of optimum pH, the growth of most microalgae species is generally known to thrive at neutral pH [14]. The pH value of culture medium largely depends on the concentration of dissolved CO₂ and its derivative compounds (i.e., CO₃²⁻ – carbonate, HCO₃³⁻ – bicarbonate). Algae consume carbon dioxide during photosynthesis and, at optimum pH, the bicarbonate present in the medium is converted back to CO₂ by the action of the algae enzyme carbonic anhydrase with the release of hydroxyl ions, which tends to increase pH [27]. Therefore, the injection of CO₂ should be carefully monitored and

controlled if used as a source of CO₂ in the system so that the pH of the medium is maintained at an optimum level, guarantying efficient photosynthesis and growth of microalgae. Moreover, the dissolved carbon concentration is also depending on other external factors like CO₂ flow rate, effective bubbling system (i.e., increasing the active surface of CO₂ molecule bubbled into the system), the retention time, the atmospheric pressure and temperature, which directly affect the solubility of the CO₂ in the media. At this stage of the model development, these aspects have not been integrated into the numerical simulations

Based on the CLD the microalgae growth kinetic model is built with *Stella Architect* © software and shown in Annex 1. The implemented stocks and flows in microalgae growth kinetic model are based on a multiplicative co-limitation model expressed as:

$$\mu = \mu_{\max} [f(T) \cdot f(N) \cdot f(P) \cdot f(C) \cdot f(I)], \quad (11)$$

where

- μ Specific growth rate, d⁻¹;
- μ_{\max} Maximum specific growth rate, d⁻¹;
- $f(T)$ Growth function for temperature;
- $f(N)$ Growth function for N as the substrate;
- $f(C)$ Growth function for C as the substrate;
- $f(P)$ Growth function for P as the substrate;
- $f(I)$ Growth function considering light attenuation.

The functions $f(x_i)$ are adapted from Steele, Monod and Haario growth models [7], [15] and can be further elaborated as:

$$\mu = \mu_{\max} \left[\theta^{T-T_{\text{ref}}} \cdot \frac{S_N}{k_{(s,N)} + S_N} \cdot \frac{S_P}{k_{(s,P)} + S_P} \cdot \frac{S_C}{k_{(s,C)} + S_C} \cdot \frac{I}{I_0} e^{\left(1 - \frac{I}{I_0}\right)} \right], \quad (12)$$

where

- S_N, S_P, S_C Concentration of substrates in the culture media, g l⁻¹;
- $k_{(s,N)}, k_{(s,P)}, k_{(s,C)}$ Half saturation constants of substrates, g l⁻¹;
- θ Temperature coefficient;
- T Culture temperature, °C;
- T_{ref} Reference temperature where growth rate is maximum, °C;
- I_0 Average solar irradiance received on the surface of the pond, $\mu\text{mol}/(\text{m}^2 \text{s})$;
- I Average solar irradiance received by the algae cells at a certain depth, $\mu\text{mol}/(\text{m}^2 \text{s})$.

Nevertheless, in the SD model developed with *Stella Architect* ©, the multiple effects on kinetic models have not been fully explored moreover, even though still represented in the given model proposed in Annex. Based on the developed model, the effect of temperature, pH, and changes of the dissolved Carbon have not been considered.

All the constants associated with the equations which are required to build the model previously described are listed in Table 1. In this study, the above model is used to simulate the growth of algae strain *Chlorella vulgaris* at each defined depths of an open raceway pond.

TABLE 1. INPUT DATA FOR MODEL FOR THE SD MODEL

Parameter	Unit	Value	Source
μ_{\max}	d^{-1}	0.248	[28]
θ	unitless	1.003	[15]
T_{ref}	Celsius	25	[15]
T	Celsius	20	[15]
$k_s(P)$	$mg\ l^{-1}$	0.001	[15]
$k_s(N)$	$mg\ l^{-1}$	0.0023	[15]
$k_s(C)$	$mg\ l^{-1}$	0.0046	[15]
Yield (P)	g of DW/ g of P	0.002	[15]
Yield (N)	g of dry weight of microalgae/ g of N	0.015	[15]
Yield (C)	g of dry weight of microalgae/ g of C	0.057	[15]
Death rate	d^{-1}	0.06	[29]
S_P	$mg\ l^{-1}$	10	[4]
S_N	$mg\ l^{-1}$	40	[4]
S_C	$mg\ l^{-1}$	1000	[4]
I_o	$\mu\text{mol}\ m^{-2}\ s^{-1}$	100	[4]
z	cm	40	[4]
dz	cm	5	[4]
Surface area of the pond	m^2	2.78	[4]
Initial algae concentration (B_0)	$g\ l^{-1}$	0.05	[4]

The biomass productivity in an open raceway pond is expressed as the amount of dry weight produced per cycle [30]. The microalgae biomass productivity calculated for each equally distributed layer can be calculated using Eq. (13):

$$P_t = (B_t - B_0) \cdot A \cdot dz \cdot 10^3, \quad (13)$$

where

- P_t Biomass productivity after time t , g;
- B_t Final biomass concentration in the relevant layer, g/l;
- B_0 Initial biomass concentration, g/l;
- A Surface area of the pond, m^2 ;
- dz Depth of each equally distributed layer, m.

4.2. Analysis of the Growth Based on Culture Depths

In this section are presented the results assuming for the simulation a ten-day microalgae growth period. The results about the analysis of the concentrations of *Chlorella vulgaris* at each layer under different initial biomass concentrations (B_0) (i.e., 0.01 g/l, 0.02 g/l, 0.04 g/l, 0.05 g/l, 0.06 g/l, 0.08 g/l and 0.1 g/l) are all reported in Annex 2.

Fig. 5 shows the trends at different culture depths considering an initial biomass concentration very diluted $B_0 = 0.01$ g/l. It can be noticed that the microalgae culture in all eight considered layers increases over the ten days. The increment of biomass follows the same exponential relationship until 6 days where the biomass concentration of all the layers

reaches slightly higher than 0.015 g/l. After that, the growth rates of each layer start to deviate slightly.

Fig. 5. Microalgae concentration at each layer at the initial concentration of $B_0 = 0.01$ g/l. Considering simulations related to different culture depth expressed in cm from the surface, i.e. $z = 0$, in specific 5 cm (simulation 1), 10 cm (simulation 2), 15 cm (simulation 3), 20 cm (simulation 4), 20 cm (simulation 4), 25 cm (simulation 5), 30 cm (simulation 6), 35 cm (simulation 7), 40 cm (simulation 8).

Fig. 6. Microalgae concentration at each layer at the initial concentration of $B_0 = 0.1$ g/l. Considering simulations related to different culture depth expressed in cm from the surface, i.e. $z = 0$, in specific 5 cm (simulation 1), 10 cm (simulation 2), 15 cm (simulation 3), 20 cm (simulation 4), 20 cm (simulation 4), 25 cm (simulation 5), 30 cm (simulation 6), 35 cm (simulation 7), 40 cm (simulation 8).

When it comes to very high initial algae concentrations ($B_0 = 0.1$ g/l), a rapid change of growth behaviour can be observed (Fig. 6). Algae present in the bottom layer starts to die due to a lack of available light. Meantime the top layer's growth rate slightly changes its behaviour into a linear function, suggesting that the top layer's growth rate becomes to follow zero-order kinetics.

The results in Annex 2 shows that when the B_0 reaches 0.08 g/l there is no change of biomass after the depth reaches 30 cm. At that point, the growth rate equals to the death rate. Hence for more concentrated cultures, which is a common approach in open raceway pond

cultivation, the optimum pond depth is around 30 cm. The overall biomass concentration after 10 days is calculated and plotted referring to the depth of the pond (see Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Final biomass concentration as a function of pond depth.

Fig. 8. Biomass productivity and the initial culture concentration relationship.

The model results suggest a similar trend described in other hypothetical models: the biomass decreases with pond depth due to light attenuation. However, for a very diluted initial biomass, the final concentrations are similar at each pond depth. When the initial culture concentration is higher, the concentration is higher at all pond depths.

4.3. Biomass Productivity

The cumulative biomass productivity, which is the total biomass produced during a particular time is calculated by summing biomass productivity in all the layers. By using the model results, the biomass productivity after ten days is calculated for the dimensions (see Table 2).

TABLE 2. MODEL OUTPUT FOR BIOMASS PRODUCTIVITY

B_0	Biomass productivity at each layer, g								Cumulative yield, g
	5 cm	10 cm	15 cm	20 cm	25 cm	30 cm	35 cm	40 cm	
0.01	4.86	4.81	4.72	4.62	4.49	4.37	4.23	4.10	25.08
0.02	9.61	9.23	8.73	8.20	7.68	7.20	6.76	6.36	41.52
0.04	18.46	16.40	14.39	12.72	11.37	10.29	9.40	8.66	57.21
0.05	22.47	19.20	16.38	14.22	12.56	11.27	10.24	9.41	60.15
0.06	26.19	21.59	18.02	15.43	13.52	12.08	10.95	10.05	61.10
0.08	32.79	25.44	20.57	17.33	15.06	13.40	12.13	11.15	58.91
0.10	38.39	28.43	22.54	18.82	16.31	14.51	13.18	12.16	53.16

The relationship between biomass productivity and the initial culture concentration from the obtained results is plotted in Fig. 8.

For low initial concentrations, Biomass productivity also is low. The productivity increases with the increase in initial concentration B_0 value up to 0.06. The biomass productivity decreases for higher values of initial biomass concentration, showing a non-linear relationship between biomass productivity and the initial culture concentration.

4.4. Validation

The kinetic models can use a function of one factor or multiple factors. Most of the models found on literature are based on a single parameter, either a substrate or light. The validation of such models is performed by saturating the system with the rest of the factors, except the variable factor. Models that consider the interactions or links between different factors include several parameters. Models that are multi-nutrient are often complex in form. Often such models have trouble in overfitting because many parameters are involved and are best applied in a wide range of environmental and nutrient conditions, with a small set of assumptions, to minimize this inherent problem [15], [31].

For this reason, the validation of the model based on the results of pilot testing stand, have not been yet realized at this stage of the research. As well as the validation of the SD model structure has not been fully investigated, even though the kinetics are in line with the ones reported in literature [4], [22].

5. CONCLUSIONS

Having precise information on microalgae biomass growth is important when designing and operating an open raceway pond. In this study, a tool for predicting the microalgae growth based on System Dynamics approach is developed. The created microalgae growth kinetic model represents a user-friendly approach for screening different factors affecting microalgae growth in outdoor open ponds.

The developed model is implemented in a straightforward manner rather than a complex simulation tool; however, the study is limited to the assumption that the pond's biomass concentration is homogeneous. The homogeneity is maintained by turbulent mixing of the pond culture with a paddlewheel mixer. In practice, the biomass is not homogeneous, and is rather concentrated at different zones. This effect can be simulated with the help of the particle tracing tool in Computational Fluid Dynamic model. Hence, it is recommended to integrate the developed System Dynamic model with a Computational Fluid Dynamic model

for a more precise growth dynamic model. The System Dynamics model can also be further developed by including several additional causal loops, which are assumed to be constant in the current model, such as pH and gas solubility.

The current microalgae growth kinetic model results suggest that the growth of microalgae in outdoor open raceway ponds is largely affected by the light attenuation, which depends on pond depth and the initial biomass concentration. For dilute initial biomass concentrations ($B_0 = 0.01$ g/l) there), no significant effect from light attenuation, which results resulting in a rate at different depths. However, when the initial biomass concentration increases, light attenuation at each pond depth becomes an influential factor for algae growth. The analysis of biomass concentration after period of ten days in relation to pond depth showed that the optimum culture depth for an open raceway pond is about 30–35 cm. According to these results, more than 35 cm deep ponds will not provide any advantage for outdoor cultivation.

After ten days, the cumulative biomass yield analysis with different initial biomass concentrations suggests that an initial concentration of 0.06 g/l has the highest biomass yield. The lower initial concentrations would require more time as the growth rate is relatively proportional to the population and higher initial concentrations would have a lower yield as high biomass concentrations lead to higher light attenuation resulting in a low growth rate at the bottom of the pond. The constants related to the mathematical model are obtained from different literature, showing imprecise results for different environmental or climatic conditions.

As mentioned at this stage the validation has not been proposed at this stage of research.

In summary, the main conclusion is that natural light can be the most limiting factor affecting microalgae growth rate in open raceway ponds. As classical open raceway ponds only receive light from the top surface, the maximum biomass that can be maintained in the culture is very low due to light attenuation. Thus, it is required to remove the culture more frequently. This proves the urgency to develop cultivation systems, where the open ponds are made with transparent materials providing higher exposure to solar irradiation. It is recommended to validate the developed model in a pilot case study.

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ANNEX 1. THE GROWTH KINETIC SD MODEL DEVELOPED IN STELLA ARCHITECT ©

ANNEX 2. MODEL RESULT FOR DIFFERENT INITIAL BIOMASS CONCENTRATIONS IN BETWEEN TWO EXTREME INITIAL VALUES

TABLE 1A. MODEL RESULT FOR DIFFERENT INITIAL BIOMASS CONCENTRATIONS IN BETWEEN TWO EXTREME INITIAL VALUES CONSIDERING THE SIMULATIONS FROM TABLE 2; SIMULATIONS RELATED TO DIFFERENT CULTURE DEPTH

Simulation Nr.	Culture depth [cm from surface, $z = 0$]
1	5
2	10
3	15
4	20
5	25
6	30
7	35
8	40